

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D3.3 Report on the conclusions of the dedicated workshops (revised version)

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
EVs	Electric vehicles
PLD	Pulsed Laser Deposition
SSB	Solid State Batteries
Gen4b	Generation 4b
LIB	Li-ion batteries
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
ML	Machine Learning
Li-ion	Lithium-ion
ASSB	anode-free all-solid-state battery
R2R	roll-to-roll
AB	Advisory Board

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Executive Summary

The **SPINMATE project** took the initiative to engage with other projects under the topics **HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-03**, **HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-05**, and **LC-BAT1-2019** to establish a solid knowledge-based around Gen 4a and Gen 4b SSBs and share Gen 4b materials-related achievements.

SPINMATE and the other seven projects established a cooperation framework—the **SOLID4B cluster**—to organise dedicated workshops and promote the internship of researchers between leading research institutions in Europe.

The **SOLID4B cluster** enhances research synergies among European-level projects on solid-state batteries, translating research data into valuable knowledge for diverse stakeholders. This cluster was built to synchronise and conjointly promote R&D topics in the electric vehicle field.

The knowledge and experience shared between different projects will support the individual performance of the projects involved while maximising the dissemination range of achievements and respective impacts.

The dedicated webinar and hybrid workshops conducted by the **SOLID4B cluster** aim to discuss, promote, and disrupt ideas regarding the safety, efficiency and sustainability of batteries and related e-mobility technologies by translating research data into valuable knowledge for diverse stakeholders, including industry leaders, researchers, and policymakers.

1. Introduction

This deliverable summarises the planned joint activities among the **SOLID4B cluster**, involving eight funded European projects under the Horizon 2020 program and Horizon Europe from the calls HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-03, HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-05, and LC-BAT1-2019. The **SPINMATE** project provides a clustering activities plan in this deliverable, considering the previously agreed activities between the SOLID4B partners.

2. The SOLID4B members

This document reports the planned activities (updated version) for the **SOLID4B cluster** led by ABEE as a project coordinator, presented by Takwa Benissa, Ph.D. and Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha, Ph.D., as part of the **SPINMATE** project. After December 2023, eight EU projects agreed to be a part of this cluster to share knowledge and exchange experiences around Gen 4a and Gen 4b SSBs and lithium metal, as it is a common topic among all the involved projects.

It also reports the main content and outputs of the first webinar, the 1st and the 2nd hybrid workshops of the **SOLID4B event series**.

In the following section, we will present the project members of the **SOLID4B cluster**, the agreed plan, and the outcomes of the first webinar. Currently, the **SOLID4B cluster** includes the following projects: **SPINMATE**, ADVAGEN, AM4BAT, HIDDEN, PULSELION, SEATBELT, SOLID, and PSIONIC.

2.1 SPINMATE Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069712

SPINMATE aims to demonstrate a scalable, sustainable, safe, and cost-effective digital-driven proof-of-concept pilot line at a TRL6 level as a first step towards the large-scale manufacturing of generation 4b (Gen 4b) SSB cells and modules to support the electrification of the automotive sector. To do so, **SPINMATE** proposes developing and implementing innovative and scalable manufacturing and processing solutions (notching/cutting, stacking and sealing/packaging steps, among others). Furthermore, new industry 4.0 and 5.0 concepts (Industrial Internet of Things - IIoT and Machine Learning - ML algorithms, Digital Twins, giga-factory line simulation, etc.) are proposed to be applied for the digitalisation of the proof-of-concept pilot line, as well as the assembly and manufacturing processes. Thus, **SPINMATE** will manufacture small 1 Ah and large 10 Ah SSB cells after the development and optimisation of the following:

- (i) advanced solid polymer electrolyte with high ionic conductivity and broad electrochemical stability,
- (ii) Li metal foil with surface treatment enabling a more stable interface as anode and
- (iii) Ni-rich layered oxide cathode with improved cycling stability.

Regarding electrodes (i.e., anode and cathode) and electrolyte processing, innovative solvent-free extrusion routes, a roll-to-roll approach, and optimised solvent casting methods are suggested. **SPINMATE**'s Gen 4b SSB cells will create a new European industry value chain towards their commercialisation.

This new generation technology will ensure:

- (i) enhanced energy densities, overcoming current LIB limitations,
- (ii) improved safety in both solutions and workers,
- (iii) increased sustainable mass production; and
- (iv) decreased carbon footprint and cost.

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2.2 ADVAGEN Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069743

To date, the battery market is dominated by lithium-ion (Li-ion) chemistries, as the energy density has more than doubled, and their costs have dropped by a factor of at least 10. However, conventional Li-ion batteries (LIB) are reaching their performance limits regarding energy density and facing safety issues. The development and production of new battery generations, such as Solid-State Batteries (SSBs), are required to create a new industry value chain in Europe towards their commercialisation. Consequently, high energy-density EU-made SSBs will ensure the supply of, among others, the automotive sector. To do so, developing and deploying new manufacturing technologies, enabling the large-scale production of SSBs, is crucial. Indeed, among the overarching themes to develop and produce sustainable batteries in the future, the BATTERY 2030+ roadmap⁴ considers manufacturability as a cross-cutting key area. Innovative and scalable manufacturing techniques to produce SSBs will accelerate cost reduction, energy savings, and enhanced safety. ADVAGEN will develop a new lithium metal (LiM) battery cell technology based on a safe, reliable, and high-performing hybrid solid-state electrolyte (LLZO-LPS based), gaining a competitive advantage over the worldwide (mainly Asian) competition. This will strengthen the EU as a technological and manufacturing leader in batteries, as specified in the ERTRAC electrification roadmap and SET-Plan Action Point-7. ADVAGEN consortium contains key EU actors in the battery sector, from industrial materials producers (CPT) battery manufacturers (ABEE) to R&D centres (IKE, CEA, IREC, TUB, CICE, POLITO, INEGI, UL, FEV) and the automotive industry (TME), covering the complete knowledge and value chain. ADVAGEN aims to re-establish European competitiveness in battery cell production by developing high-performance, affordable and safe batteries.

2.3 AM4BAT Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069756

Next-generation lithium-ion batteries will need to offer higher energy and power densities at a lower cost. Current battery manufacturing is struggling to improve these key metrics further. The EU-funded AM4BAT project will leverage additive manufacturing technologies for fabricating 3D lithium-ion batteries. Using vat photopolymerisation 3D printing, the aim is to develop a high-performance battery with an energy density of 400 Wh/kg for electric vehicles. AM4BAT outcomes will contribute to creating a sustainable European battery manufacturing value chain, helping the EU succeed in the electric mobility rollout.

AM4BAT will develop innovative component materials and assemble an anode-free all-solid-state battery (ASSB) manufactured by a cost-competitive and sustainable VAT photo-polymerisation 3D printing. The objective is to reach a high-performance battery with an energy density of 400 Wh/kg and 1000 Wh/L for electric vehicle applications. This will be achieved by developing materials, including,

- (i) single crystal NMC811 with superior energy,
- (ii) LNMO Co-free and higher voltage for power AM4BAT variant,
- (iii) doped LLZO with different sizes from 0.5 to 5µm and 50-100 nm for higher loading in the HSE,
- (iv) novel acrylic, nanocellulose, sustainable photocurable polymer.

The materials will be optimised for their processing by additive manufacturing. AM4BAT will then validate the technology via 3-Ah pouch cells reaching TRL5, evaluate manufacturability, and conduct a complete sustainability assessment and a recycling study to support 'customers' uptake. Identified stakeholder groups and other research initiatives will be actively involved to ensure the dissemination of AM4BAT results and broader 'users' acceptance. With its ambitious concept based on cutting-edge 3D printed ASSB and a strong consortium involving the whole value chain from material providers to an OEM, AM4BAT aims to overcome the remaining

technological obstacles of the Gen 4b technology as specified in the work programme and accomplish the urgent shorter-term needs of the battery industry: to make Gen 4b batteries a viable technology beyond 2025. In the longer term, the AM4BAT outcomes will contribute to creating a sustainable European battery manufacturing value chain, helping the EU succeed in the electric mobility roll-out and accelerate the energy transition.

2.4 HIDDEN Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069681

The EU-funded HIDDEN project plans to develop self-healing processes that could extend the lifespan of lithium-metal batteries by 50 %, thus allowing the production of durable next-generation batteries with 50 % higher energy density than traditional lithium-ion batteries over a total lifetime. The primary focus will be producing novel self-healing thermotropic liquid crystalline electrolytes and piezoelectric separator technologies. Multiscale modelling of electrolyte design will enable researchers to gain valuable insight into dendrite growth that plagues lithium-metal batteries. The project brings together partners from academia and industry with expertise in battery chemistry and physics, material modelling, printing and coating, and industrial battery cell assembly.

2.5 PULSELiON Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069686

The EU aims to have at least 30 million zero-emission vehicles on the roads by 2030. In-house production of high-performance battery technology is vital to the broader adoption of electric vehicles. The EU-funded PULSELiON project aims to develop the manufacturing technology for Generation 4b solid-state batteries. These batteries will comprise a lithium-metal anode, sulfide solid electrolytes and a nickel-rich nickel-manganese-cobalt cathode. A novel pulsed laser deposition technique will be adapted and modified into a single-step vacuum process to safely and efficiently manufacture the 'batteries' anode components. The cathode layer will be produced using conventional wet processing techniques. Europe's objective to have 30 million electric vehicles (EVs) by 2030 can only be achieved by large-scale, in-house production of highly effective and performant batteries. Developing solid-state battery technologies could improve lithium metal solid-state batteries' energy density and safety. The PULSELiON project aims to develop a Gen 4b solid-state batteries (SSBs) manufacturing process based on lithium-metal anode, sulfide solid electrolytes, and Nickel-rich NMC cathode. A novel pulsed laser deposition technique developed by PULSELiON will be adapted and modified into a single-step vacuum process to safely and efficiently manufacture anode components composed of lithium metal, protective layers, and sulfide-based solid electrolytes. The cathode layer will be made based on conventional wet processing techniques. Initially, the anode and cathode layers will be developed on a small scale to make coin and monolayer cells to optimise the materials and process. SSB cells will be developed with optimised process routes and upscaled to a pilot line proof-of-concept (TRL 6) by manufacturing large-scale solid-state batteries (10 Ah). Digitalisation will be incorporated into the process modelling task with the inputs obtained from process upscaling and cell testing tasks, enabling efficient process optimisation.

2.6 SEATBELT Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069726

Electric vehicles are powered by batteries, which are the most essential part. However, the demand for electric vehicles is increasing so fast that it will soon outpace battery cell production. The EU-funded SEATBELT project will help to pave the road towards a cost-effective, robust, all-solid-state lithium battery comprising sustainable materials by 2026. Specifically, it will achieve the first technological milestone of developing a battery cell that meets the needs of the electric vehicle industry. The low-cost cell will be safe by design with sustainable and recyclable materials, reaching high energy densities and long cyclability per the 2030 EU targets. The project will be the starting point of the first EU solid-state battery value chain.

As of 2025, new generations of Li batteries based on silicon/carbon (Gen. 4a) and Li metal (Gen. 4b) anode will take over the current Li-ion device, where a non-flammable solid-one replaces flammable liquid electrolyte. However, only all-solid-state Gen. 4b Li batteries are expected to fulfil the needed cell gravimetric energy density specifications demanded by electromobility and stationary applications. Therefore, SEATBELT aims to generate a local EU industry that revolves around a cost-effective, robust, all-solid-state Li battery comprising sustainable materials by 2026. SEATBELT intends to achieve the first technological milestone of developing a battery cell (TRL5), meeting the needs of the Electric Vehicle (EV) and stationary industry. The low-cost SEATBELT cell is safe by design with sustainable and recyclable materials, reaching high energy densities (>380 Wh/kg) and long cyclability (>500 cycles) by 2026, which is in line with the 2030 EU targets. The cells are produced by a low-cost solvent-free extrusion process comprising a combination of innovative materials: thin Li metal, hybrid electrolyte, a safe cathode active material without critical materials and a thin Al current collector. The cell design is optimised by interface (operando and atomistic modelling) and process (machine learning) methodologies. In addition, new in situ imaging instrumentation will be developed to investigate safety properties and mechanical deformation to assess cell safety in actual conditions. An innovative recycling cycle from materials to cell level will also be established. Thus, SEATBELT will be the starting point of the first EU all-solid-state battery value chain, whose main players in RTD and Industry sectors are within the consortium. So, cells and modules will cycle using industrially relevant protocols dedicated to EV and stationary applications. SEATBELT consortium comprises 14 beneficiary partners, 3 affiliated entities, and one associated partner, from 7 European countries with an overall budget of 7851448.50€.

2.7 SOLiD Project – Grant Agreement ID: 101058179

In the world of batteries, a solid-state design has advantages over batteries that use a liquid - including lithium-ion batteries. Safer and higher in energy density, the solid-state battery is considered the future generation of batteries. The EU-funded SOLiD project will create a sustainable and cost-efficient pilot-scale manufacturing process. It will use roll-to-roll (R2R) dry extrusion coating to blend cathode active material, solid polymer electrolytes, and conducting additives. The metallic lithium anode will be produced by R2R pulsed laser deposition. SOLiD aims to enable sustainable manufacturing of advanced high-performance Generation 4b (solid-state) Li-ion batteries to support electromobility with a minimised amount of critical raw materials (Co and Li) and superior performance and safety.

The SOLiD project will create a sustainable and cost-efficient pilot scale manufacturing process for a high energy density, safe and easily recyclable solid-state Li-metal battery. We will use roll-to-roll (R2R) dry extrusion coating to blend cathode active material, solid polymer electrolyte, and conducting additives. R2R slot die-coated primers on the cathode current collector will enhance the cell's adhesion, performance and corrosion resistance. The polymer electrolyte layer will be R2R coated, using an optimal design for the slot die head. We will utilise cost-efficient R2R pulsed laser deposition for the Li metal anode, which minimises the Li thickness down to 5 µm. The Li metal production will be combined with an inline process for interfacial engineering to ensure compatibility with the other layers and stability. The process development will be supported by digitalisation methods to go towards zero-defect and cost-efficient manufacturing.

The proposed methods enable sustainable manufacturing of Gen. 4b solid-state batteries with a minimised amount of critical raw materials (Co and Li) and with superior performance and safety: The protective layers enable the use of NMC811, which reduces the amount of Co to a minimum without compromising the lifetime, and PLD process helps to minimise the Li thickness. Dry coating eliminates toxic solvents and energy-consuming drying steps, and digital quality control will reduce the amount of waste. The thickness of each layer will be minimised to reach

an energy density above 900 Wh/l. Cost-effective production methods and yield maximisation will reduce the cost. The solid electrolyte and the protective interlayers guarantee safety and long cycle life. Supported by life-cycle thinking and stakeholder engagement, the SOLiD project will enable the design of a future sustainable solid-state battery factory.

2.8 PSIONIC Project – Grant agreement ID: 101069703

The PSIONIC project is a four-year initiative funded by the European Union under its Horizon Europe Research and Innovation program. The project's primary goal is to support the development of all-solid-state battery technology. The PSIONIC project aims to design all-solid-state batteries and prototype cells using cost-effective solvent-free extrusion processes. The battery will utilise a lithium metal anode and Lithium Nickel-rich Cobalt Manganese oxide (NCM) cathode comprising 85% nickel and optimally designed polymer electrolyte interfaces. This unique combination will allow the battery to achieve unprecedented levels of safety, high ionic conductivity/transport, and higher energy and power density.

Key milestones include:

- (i) Project initiation in July 2022.
- (ii) Training sessions for researchers, ensuring high-impact research publications and fostering partnerships.
- (iii) Securing patents and intellectual property rights for the PSIONIC battery technology.
- (iv) Showcasing prototype pouch cells with over 5Ah capacity at Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 5 to 6 by project conclusion.
- (v) Enhancing cell chemistry and design to boost performance, setting the stage for scaling up production and advancing to TRL 7-9.
- (vi) Outlining a definitive roadmap to 2030 and beyond for achieving TRL 8-9 and demonstrating the technology in Battery Electric Vehicles (BEVs) like cars and buses.

Through its research and innovation actions, the PSIONIC project aims to contribute to the technological advancements of all-solid-state Li-ion batteries in terms of safety, reliability, performance, cost, and sustainability. The project's outcome has the potential to enable higher uptake by the electromobility sector and end consumers, paving the way towards climate neutrality and green energy transition.

3. SOLID4B cluster identity

We designed the logo below for all communication and dissemination materials to give this cluster a visual identity (Figure 1).

Figure 1: SOLID4B Logo.

Figure 2 showed the particular dedicated LinkedIn page under the name of the **SOLID4B cluster** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/solid4b-cluster/>) was created in October 2022 with around 839 followers and experts on batteries worldwide (May 2024). All the partners of this cluster agreed on the name and the slogan of this cluster in October after sharing a voting poll.

"SOLID4B cluster: Going Solid for safer batteries."

Figure 2: SOLID4B LinkedIn page.

INOVA, the Leader of SPINMATE WP9 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation), managed the communication activities of the SOLID4B cluster – with the support from SPINMATE coordinator ABEE – promoting the cluster and its activities with the development of marketing digital materials and engaging with stakeholders through social media. The events organised under the SOLID4B cluster were promoted and covered on its LinkedIn page, creating awareness of the events and topics selected, attracting participants, and building the online network of SOLID4B members to disseminate the cluster activities, which were supported by cluster members’ specific social media.

4. Internal communication

Microsoft Teams platform (Figure 3) was implemented to ensure easy but effective communication and collaboration between the cluster's partners. All the projects' coordinators and the communication leaders of all the partners were added to this repository to ensure an easily accessible and reliable communication infrastructure has been created.

Figure 3: Teams Platform.

5. Cluster activities plan

The SOLID4B cluster enhances research synergies among European-level projects addressing the safety of batteries and related technologies by translating research data into useful knowledge for diverse stakeholders. This cluster was built to synchronise and conjointly promote the R&D topics on electric vehicles.

After a meeting with all the project coordinators and the communication partners of all the project partners on the 18th of April 2023, an action plan has been established as below:

- Online events/webinars and workshops will take place every six months.
- **SPINMATE** and **AM4BAT** will organise two onsite clustering workshops (one workshop per project).
- The first workshop will take place around the mid-term report to ensure that the maximum of partners can join.
- From the **SEATBELT** project, **INP Grenoble**, represented by **Didier Devaux**, organises a workshop/training to disseminate project results every two years at the European level. The cluster results can be used to disseminate cluster activities and results at the next workshop/training that will take place in **2025**.

- As the publication target for all the cluster partners is challenging, we agreed to have at least one white paper to disseminate the cluster results around **2025**. All the partners agreed that the peer-reviewed results could be used in the white papers.
- The advisory boards of the projects can join as keynote speakers for the webinars and workshops.
- Create a list of the potential events the partners can attend jointly as a cluster.

6. SOLID4B cluster: 1st Webinar

6.1. Webinar agenda and topics

The first webinar of the **SOLID4B cluster** took place on June 26, 2023, from 10 AM to 12.30 PM, under the theme "Lithium metal anode production methods: State of the art, challenges, and future perspective," as illustrated in the agenda below (Figure 4).

Since advertising the webinar on social media for the first time on June 7, 2023, the webinar has attracted the attention of 175 subscribers, which reflects the cluster's impact on the battery world, specifically as it is the first edition. It indicates that many people were interested in receiving updates and notifications about the webinar.

The first agenda advertisement and office forum (<https://forms.office.com/e/Uqja6C9YK2>) was created and shared on social media and through emails with all the cluster partners based on privacy regulations and data protection guidelines. The aim of making that subscription forum was essentially to:

- **Simplify Subscription:** The office forum provides a centralised platform where individuals can easily subscribe to receive updates and notifications about upcoming steps. By having a dedicated space for subscriptions, we were able to streamline the process and make it more convenient for interested participants to sign up.
- **Collect Data:** The forum included different fields where participants could provide information about themselves or their organisations. This can consist of data such as the company or institution they belong to, their country of origin, and their interest in interacting with the speakers. Gathering this data helps us understand the audience demographics, interests, and preferences, which can inform future webinar planning and content creation.
- **Identify targeted Engagement:** We could tailor our communication and engagement strategies according to the data collected.
- **Evaluate the interaction with the experts:** The office forum showed our participants' interest in engaging with the experts or speakers involved in the webinar. Considering this information, we designed the Microsoft Teams platform by creating a Q&A section where the participants can ask questions, share their thoughts, or request specific topics or speakers for future events. This interactive element fosters engagement, encourages participation, and strengthens the connection between the audience and the experts.
- **Analyse the Data:** The data collected through the office forum were analysed to gain insights into the audience composition, preferences, and needs. This analysis helped to identify trends, understand the webinar's impact on different segments, and make informed decisions about future webinar planning and content creation.

Figure 4: Agenda of the first webinar.

6.2. Main Results

This webinar focused on the different Lithium metal anode production methods utilised in the **SOLID4B cluster** projects. The session was opened by Solid4B founders Takwa Benissa and Andrea Martinez (**SPINMATE**), who explained the **SOLID4B cluster** goals and scope and introduced the involved partners. After a BEPA (Batteries European Partnership) welcome, the ADVAGEN and HIDDEN project representatives introduced the topic. They discussed the different lithium metal production methods (Jokin Rikarte) and the self-healing methods (Marja Vilkmán). The next block of presentations focused on vapor-based techniques for lithium metal production, including talks from **SPINMATE** (Joel Omale), PULSELiON (Ville Kekkonen), and SOLID (Sara Pakseresht) project representatives. Next, Milad Madinehei (AM4BAT project) presented electrochemical lithium production for an anode-less battery. The final talk of the webinar by Gaetan Cabon (SEATBELT project) focused on the state-of-the-art industrial lithium metal anode processing by extrusion and its challenges. Finally, a roundtable discussion led by Timothé Perruchoud (BEPA) closed the webinar.

Figure 5 shows the welcome session delivered by BEPA focused on introducing the Batt4EU Partnership. The Batt4EU Partnership is a co-programmed partnership under Horizon Europe that gathers the European Commission and BEPA and brings together all the European battery stakeholders interested in getting involved in Horizon Europe. The Batt4EU vision and scope and the working groups were explained, providing the webinar attendees with a clear understanding of how Batt4EU fosters solid-state battery projects. Lastly, the attendees were encouraged to join BEPA and attend the upcoming BEPA events and workshops to create synergies in the European battery community.

WG1 NEW AND EMERGING BATTERY TECHNOLOGIES	WG2 RAW MATERIALS AND RECYCLING
WG3 ADVANCED MATERIALS	WG4 CELL DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING
WG5 MOBILE APPLICATIONS AND INTEGRATION	WG6 STATIONARY APPLICATIONS AND INTEGRATION

BEPA
Battery European Partnership Association

Set the European R&I landscape for the Battery Industry

BEPA members can join **Working Groups**, giving the opportunity to:

- Define and draft topics for calls in Horizon Europe Work Programmes on batteries;
- Update the Strategic R&I Agenda of Batt4EU summarising the key research priorities for the battery sector;
- Get first-hand information on the strategic R&I roadmap and priority of research topics;
- Get access to impactful research findings generated in Europe (in ongoing Horizon Europe projects).

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Figure 5: Snapshot of BEPA session presented by **Timothé Perruchoud**.

Jokin Rikarte (ADVAGEN project) introduced the webinar topic by presenting the state-of-the-art challenges and future perspectives of lithium metal anode production methods (Figure 6). The lithium metal anode benefits, challenges, and improvement strategies were introduced first to provide the webinar attendees with the necessary background. Afterwards, the standard industrial process of lithium production was compared with the alternative methods, which included the PVD techniques, melting and slurry approaches, and electrodeposition and anodeless routes. The different methods were compared regarding the process feasibility and the resulting lithium metal anode quality, providing the webinar attendees with a comprehensive overview of the different lithium metal anode production routes.

Figure 6: Snapshot of session presented **ADVAGEN** by **Jokin Rikarte**.

Marja Vilkmán (HIDDEN project) has introduced Li-metal batteries and their benefits for the automotive sector, as well as the Li-metal issues that impact the battery's lifetime (Figure 7). After an overview of different electrolytes that can be used in the Li-metal battery, different methods to increase the lifetime of the Li-metal batteries, including preventative/autonomous and curative self-healing methods, were discussed. The HIDDEN project approach was explained once the webinar attendees were familiar with the different self-healing methods.

Figure 7: Snapshot of HIDDEN session presented by Marja Vilkmán.

The next block of presentations focused on the vapour-based lithium metal production techniques, which were opened by Joel Omale (SPINMATE) and concentrated on physical vapour deposition processes, including evaporation and sputtering (Figure 8). These two processes were explained in great detail, describing why evaporation is more suitable for large-scale lithium production while sputtering is most suited for lithium protective coatings. It was also demonstrated how these vapour-based lithium production techniques are integrated into the SPINMATE project, familiarising the webinar attendees with the SPINMATE concept.

Figure 8: Snapshot of SPINMATE session presented by Joel Omale.

Ville Kekkonen (PULSELiON project) delivered the next talk on vapour-based techniques, pulsed laser deposition (PLD) of lithium metal and protective coatings. The PLD technique was explained in detail, highlighting the key benefits of this lithium production method and illustrating the different tools used (Figure 9). The webinar attendees could see some experimental data showcasing what the lithium metal deposited on a copper current collector using PLD looks like and its performance. Finally, the upscaling of PLD was discussed as well.

Figure 9: Snapshot of PULSELiON session presented by Ville Kekkonen.

Sara Pakseresht (SOLiD project) has presented atomic layer deposition (ALD) coatings for lithium metal stabilisation. The webinar attendees familiarised themselves with the unique benefits of the ALD technique. An overview of different ALD coatings mentioned in the literature was provided, and the experimental data showcasing how ALD coating improves battery performance was discussed, engaging the webinar attendees (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Snapshot of SOLiD session presented by Sara Pakseresht.

The following presentation by Milad Madinehei (AM4BAT) was centred around the electrochemical lithium production for an anode-less battery (Figure 11). The AM4BAT project concept and objectives, as well as the workflow and work packages, were described, familiarising the webinar attendees with the AM4BAT project and the typical structure and organisation of a European project. The challenges of designing an anode-free battery were explained, and AM4BAT strategies were used to address these challenges. A few remarks about the

7. SOLID4B cluster: 1st Hybrid Workshop (Liège, Belgium)

7.1. Workshop agenda and topics

The second agenda of the **SOLID4B cluster** is a **Hybrid Workshop** on December 12, 2023, from 1:30 to 5.30 PM under the theme "Solid State Li-Metal Batteries Towards A Circular Economy: Potentials Vs. Challenges." This agenda is in conjunction with celebrating Innovation and Circular Economy in the Walloon Region, or Circular Wallonia Days (Figure 13). For the SOLID4B cluster, the **Hybrid Workshop** agenda is illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Circular Wallonia Days poster.

[The registration page](#) showed 12 speakers from various backgrounds and with multiple levels of expertise. It was shared through the social media of the SOLID4B cluster and reposted by all of the cluster projects' pages. Besides gathering experts and cluster projects, this hybrid workshop event is also where the SPINMATE partners interact with the Advisory Board (AB) members. Further, not only inviting AB members of SPINMATE, the SOLID4B cluster also develops a discussion panel session for AB members across the projects inside the SOLID4B cluster.

Figure 14: Agenda of the first hybrid workshop.

7.2. Sub-topics and discussion contents

The first hybrid workshop mainly focuses on the research, innovation, and financial impact of solid-state battery development in the case of circular economy potentials brought by the **SOLID4B cluster** projects. The location host of the event opened the session, Lionel Fourdrinier from CRM (**SEATBELT**), who explained the innovation and circular economy in the Walloon region. He also acts as an opener for the hybrid workshop agenda (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Snapshot of the opening session presented by Lionel Fourdrinier.

After that, Takwa Benissa and Kunsulu Nurekeyeva (**SPINMATE**) explained the SOLID4B cluster under the theme “Unveiling insights and lessons from collaborative clustering endeavours” (Figure 16). Emerging battery technologies are set to revolutionise the electrification of various transport and mobile machinery, encompassing everything from vehicles on roads to those traversing water, skies, and rails alongside non-road mobile equipment. Advanced lithium-ion batteries stand out for their affordability, efficiency, safety, thermal resilience, and eco-friendliness, presenting a viable path for mass production and adoption within the mobility industry. To enhance its competitive edge, there is a pressing need to fortify Europe’s position in the global battery market, especially in cell production. The key to achieving this is the demonstration of batteries that not only last longer and perform better in energy and power density but are also safer. Furthermore, expanding Europe’s capabilities and infrastructure for materials modelling to support this growth is crucial. The ultimate goal is to establish a method for the mass production of fourth-generation battery technology in Europe that is both cost-efficient and environmentally friendly, minimising carbon emissions and ecological impact. Those key performance indicators for European projects could be achieved collectively through the clustering projects’ collaboration activity, for which the **SOLID4B cluster** is an answer.

Figure 16: Snapshot of SOLID4B session presented by Takwa Benissa and Kunsulu Nurekeyeva.

Figure 17 shows that BEPA delivered a topic about battery research priorities in Europe (Batt4EU SRIA), which focused on introducing the Batt4EU Partnership and SRIA’s new structure. Significant legislative and political developments are shaping the battery industry’s future. This includes the introduction of the Batteries Regulation, the RePower EU, and the Fit for 55 package, alongside the Critical Raw Materials Act and the Net-Zero Industry Act. These initiatives underscore the European Union’s commitment to a more sustainable and environmentally friendly approach to battery production and usage, highlighted further by the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework and the proposed PFAS ban. Additionally, the EU Court of Auditors is reviewing spending in the battery value chain, emphasising the need for accountability and efficient use of resources. On the market and industrial front, there has been a noticeable spike in the price of raw materials, driven by increased demand for Energy Storage Systems (ESS) storage and non-EV mobile applications. This demand surge coincides with the commissioning of new gigafactories, which promises to bolster production capacity significantly. Innovations such as breakthroughs in Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP), Sodium-ion (Na-ion), and

semi-solid state batteries are setting the stage for more efficient and cost-effective energy storage solutions. Furthermore, the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) in the United States is poised to have profound implications for the global battery market, influencing investment flows and strategic priorities. On the organisational side, the formation of Joint Batteries Europe and the BEPA Working Groups marks a collaborative effort to foster innovation, share knowledge, and streamline efforts across the battery value chain. These developments collectively signal a dynamic and transformative period for the battery industry, with wide-ranging implications for environmental sustainability, market competitiveness, and technological advancement.

Figure 17: Snapshot of BEPA session presented by Bozorg Khanbaei.

Javier Yélamo Mayorga from the SPINMATE, ADVAGEN, and PULSELiON projects explained the recycling challenges for next-generation solid-state batteries (Figure 18). Besides focusing on the recycling process for batteries, he also described the potential approaches for solid-state battery research recycling activities such as Li metal conversion, electrolyte recovery through washing or precipitation process, cathode material downstream, recommendations for cell design, and recycling up-scaling.

Figure 18: Snapshot of SPINMATE, ADVAGEN, and PULSELiON session presented by Javier Yélamo Mayorga.

In Figure 19, Luís Miguel Oliveira from the SPINMATE project introduced the bright European future through sustainable solid-state battery innovation and technology. He explained the concept of sustainability framework:

- (i) Life cycle assessment (LCA);
- (ii) Life cycle costing (LCC);
- (iii) Material flow cost accounting (MFCA); and
- (iv) Implementing life cycle inventory to assess the whole process.

Figure 19: Snapshot of SPINMATE session presented by Luís Miguel Oliveira.

Massimo De Pieri presents the topic of eco-design criteria for next-generation batteries from the SEATBELT project (Figure 20). There, he opened with a general overview of the European sustainability framework transition from Batteries Directive 2006/66/EC as the 1st European action on batteries, the batteries directive updated for the first time in 2020, and the 2nd update of the Batteries Directive in 2023 (New Battery Regulation). From strategic roadmap to effectively implement sustainability into the battery value chain, values to be achieved to reach the strategic goal as KPIs, methodological frameworks to measure qualitative KPIs and manage change (eco-design approach), until tools to be used to measure quantitative KPIs, which will lead to the LCA activities.

Figure 20: Snapshot of SEATBELT session presented by Massimo De Pieri.

The last topic, in Figure 21, the sustainability aspects of an anode-free solid-state battery made by 3D printing, was delivered by Maeva Lavigne Philippot from the AM4BAT project. She mainly explained the AM4BAT goals and project insight regarding the anode-free approach for potential solid-state battery development. She also conducted the interactive session using Mentimeter to learn more about the audience's perspective regarding LCA in battery development.

Figure 21: Snapshot of AM4BAT session presented by Maeva Lavigne Philippot.

The 1st **SOLID4B cluster** hybrid workshop closed with the discussion panel with the hot topic of New Battery Regulation 2023, with the moderator from BEPA (Bozorg Khanbaei), and several experts, Marja Vilkmann (HIDDEN and SOLiD projects), Xavier Randrema and Adrien Mery (RENAULT), Patrick Van den Bossche (AGORIA), and Johan Blondelle (European Commission). Besides the topic, this closing session is also a potential interaction for the AB from across the projects under the **SOLID4B cluster**, especially **SPINMATE**. Of note is that the success story for the agenda is also supported by the media campaign of the event organised by the AM4BAT project on stakeholder engagement.

8. SOLID4B cluster: 2nd Hybrid Workshop (Ninove, Belgium)

8.1. Workshop agenda and topics

The **SOLID4B cluster** 3rd agenda is the 2nd **Hybrid Workshop** that took place on the 15th of April, 2024, from 12:30 to 5.00 PM under the theme "Scaling Up High Energy Density Solid-State Batteries: A Lab-To-Pilot Line Perspective". This agenda is held in Ninove on the first day of the general assembly meeting of **SPINMATE**. The **Hybrid Workshop** agenda is illustrated in Figure 22, with the 10 experts from various batteries' sub-levels. Like the previous hybrid workshop, the SOLID4B cluster also develops a round table to be a dynamic session for AB members across the projects inside the SOLID4B cluster, especially **SPINMATE** AB members.

Figure 22: Agenda of the second hybrid workshop.

8.2. Sub-topics and discussion contents

The second hybrid workshop primarily discussed the challenges in scaling solid-state battery technology, from the lab to the pilot scale, faced by the **SOLID4B cluster** projects. The agenda is conducted offline in the Mauritz, Ninove and online through Microsoft Teams. It was opened by Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha (SPINMATE, ADVAGEN, and SOLiD) as the event host. Then, it continues with the offline session technical insight regarding the lab to prototyping process challenges by June Blanco from the SPINMATE project. After she opened with the introduction of the CICenergyGUNE, she continued with the challenges of optimising the manufacturing process, selecting suitable materials, addressing design issues, and ensuring the technical and economic feasibility of the final battery products. June explained the topic consists of three main challenges in solid-state battery development: (1) from lab to prototyping process;

(2) from a solvent-based to a solvent-free process; and (3) from laminate to a roll-to-roll (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Snapshot of SPINMATE session presented by June Blanco.

Then, Jan Hilhorst (**SEATBELT**) remotely presented a session regarding the scaling up of inorganic battery materials: optimising chemical syntheses for manufacturability (Figure 24). He stated explicitly the scaling-up process always started with the lab scale: (1) upscaling and optimisation of recipes, small-to-mid-amount of samples; pilot scale: (1) dedicated pilot line, (2) mid-amount of samples, (3) optimisation of recipe for further process; and production scale: (1) flexible plants, (2) modern equipments with continuous process, (3) final recipes with automation processes, and (4) large amount of samples to produce.

Figure 24: Snapshot of SEATBELT session presented by Jan Hilhorst.

Still, the online speaker, Franco Zanotto (**PULSELiON**), took over the session with an interesting topic of digital twins for upscaling all-solid-state battery cathode manufacturing (Figure 25). He starts with the conventional process of solid-state battery manufacturing, which needs multiple steps, a complex fabrication process, trial-error optimisation, and unknown effects of fabrication on microstructure to get a single cell with particular energy density, specific lifetime, and

uncertain safety. Further, he explained various case studies to improve the conventional processes through digital twins for battery manufacturing.

Figure 25: Snapshot of PULSELiON session presented by Franco Zanotto.

Later, an advisory board member of ADVAGEN, Daniela Fontana (SPINMATE), continued the next workshop session with another practical knowledge of solid-state battery manufacturing (Figure 26). She tried to balance the explanation from the challenges and opportunities of solid-state battery manufacturing. She started with an essential question about the changing processes once we move from the liquid-state to the all-solid-state battery system. Then, the state-of-the-art Li-ion battery production routes vs solid-state battery systems and their effect. Ultimately, she closed with another question regarding whether the winning technology will be driven by machinery, including battery manufacturing processes and developments.

Figure 26: Snapshot of SPINMATE session presented by Daniela Fontana.

Figure 27 shows Andy Schena (ADVAGEN, PULSELiON, SOLiD, and SPINMATE), who gave us a critical reminder regarding the instrument and process point of view for the upscaling production of solid-state batteries. At least five sub-topics he explained regarding:

- (i) from glove box to dry room;
- (ii) from grams to kilograms;
- (iii) from equipment to a continuous process;
- (iv) Quality, Safety, and Environment (QSE), Infrastructures, etc.; and
- (v) From lab to pilot scale.

Figure 27: Snapshot of **ADVAGEN**, **PULSELiON**, **SOLiD**, and **SPINMATE** session presented by **Andy Schena**.

As a workshop session closing, Milad Mosallaei (**SOLiD**) explicitly presented the challenges in formulating and processing dry extrudable cathode layers for solid-state batteries (Figure 28). He explained the successful story behind the lab-scale dry extrusion of cathode materials production using VTT's extruder technology. However, despite the success achieved at the lab level, the pilot scale level still becomes a big issue. From the consideration of batch mixing of a large amount of cathode compound (e.g., twin-screw extruder), which is time-consuming, then applied extrusion of a thin layer (e.g., using a flat film die) with a single-screw extruder onto current collector foil in continuous operation, those two processes are still facing challenges:

- (i) Rheological properties; processability into a thin film
- (ii) Homogeneity and adhesion of the cathode layer (target thickness?)
- (iii) Exposure of the material to the processing environment (?)
- (iv) Roll-to-roll processing.

Lab scale dry extrusion

- ▶ Extrusion of polymer + cathode and conductive materials
- ▶ Challenges
 - ▶ Dispersion issue
 - ▶ Agglomeration
 - ▶ Degradation
 - ▶ Die clogging
 - ▶ Extruder wear
- ▶ Remedies
 - ▶ Optimization of processing conditions
 - ▶ Modification of polymer viscosity
 - ▶ Processing aids (e.g., dispersion agent)

Figure 28: Snapshot of SOLiD session presented by Milad Mosallaei.

The 2nd **SOLID4B cluster** hybrid workshop closed with an interactive session through Mentimeter App led by Anish Patil (**ADVAGEN**) and round table discussion panel with the topic of the significant breakthroughs towards upscaling the solid-state batteries, with Bozorg Khanbaei (**BEPA**) as the moderator, and battery experts, Daniela Fontana (**SPINMATE**), Patrick Van den Bossche (**AGORIA**), and Gabriele Ferrara (**AVERE**). Two of the three experts in this session (Patrick and Gabriele) represent **SPINMATE**'s AB members.

9. Statistics and impacts

9.1. Questions and polling results

On average, ~200 individuals attended the webinar and hybrid workshops (online and offline) among the 250 registered participants from different countries and organisations. This indicates an attendance rate of approximately 80%. While it is common for some registered participants to not attend the live event due to scheduling conflicts or other reasons, a >75% attendance rate suggests a relatively high level of interest and engagement.

To engage more the audience and the speakers, an online poll was shared at the end of the webinar and hybrid workshops to reply to three main questions:

- **How would you rate this webinar overall?**
- **What percentage of the information was new to you?**
- **What are your suggestions for the subsequent editions?**

When participants were asked to rate the overall webinar and the hybrid workshops experience, the average rating received was 4.1 out of 5, as illustrated in Figure 29. This indicates a highly positive response from the participants, as most rated passed the average and close to the maximum score.

A 4.1 out of 5 rating suggests that the participants found the webinar and the hybrid workshops informative, engaging, and valuable. It indicates high satisfaction with the content, delivery, and overall experiences. Participants likely felt the webinar and hybrid workshops met or exceeded their expectations and provided meaningful insights or knowledge.

Moreover, it's worth noting that a rating of 4.1 out of 5 leaves room for improvement, as it is a very positive rating. However, it also suggests that some minor areas could be enhanced to achieve a higher rating in future editions.

The average rating of 4.1 out of 5 reflects a successful webinar and hybrid workshops. The participants received well and indicated that the organisers and presenters effectively delivered a valuable and engaging session.

Moreover, the feedback provided by the audience regarding the percentage of information that was new to them indicates that, on average, they estimated it to be between 75% and 100% (Figure 30). This range suggests that a significant part of the webinar and the hybrid workshops content contained new and valuable information for the participants.

Elaborating on this feedback implies that the webinar and the hybrid workshops successfully delivered substantial fresh insights, knowledge, or perspectives to the audience. Participants found a significant portion of the content informative and thought-provoking, expanding their understanding of the topic discussed.

A range of 75% to 100% indicates that while a substantial portion of the webinar and the hybrid workshops covered new information, some aspects may have been familiar or already known to the participants. This could be due to variations in the participants' prior knowledge or expertise in the subject matter.

Nevertheless, the fact that most of the content was perceived as new highlights the value provided by the webinar and the hybrid workshops. It suggests that the organisers and presenters effectively presented novel information or provided fresh insights that resonated with the audience's interests and needs.

The feedback on the percentage of new information showcases that the webinar and the hybrid workshops successfully fulfilled their purpose of delivering valuable and engaging content that expanded participants' knowledge and understanding of the topic. It indicates that the organisers and presenters could present informative material aligned with the participants' expectations and desire for new insights.

Moving forward, this feedback can further enhance future webinar and the hybrid workshops editions by providing substantial new and relevant information to ensure continued engagement and interest from the audience, building upon the first edition's success.

Figure 29: Overall rate.

Regarding the third question of the online poll, the audience's suggestions for the upcoming webinar and the hybrid workshops topics provide valuable insights into their interests and areas of focus. Here below is an analysis of each suggested topic:

- **Cost assessment and techno-economic analysis of solid-state battery production:** This topic suggests that the audience is interested in understanding the economic aspects of solid-state battery manufacturing. They want to explore the costs involved, evaluate the feasibility of production, and assess the financial viability of solid-state battery technology.
- **Progress in solid-state electrolytes:** This topic indicates that the audience is keen to learn about advancements and developments related to solid-state electrolytes. They are interested in staying updated on the latest research, breakthroughs, and innovations in this specific area of battery technology.
- **Way of optimising anodes for the following battery generations:** This topic highlights the audience's interest in exploring ways to optimise anodes for future battery generations. They want to delve into the techniques, materials, or strategies that can enhance battery anodes' performance, efficiency, and lifespan, which play a crucial role in overall battery performance.
- **Real technical challenges in projects and detailed discussions on those:** This suggestion indicates that the audience is seeking in-depth talks about the practical difficulties faced in real-world projects related to battery technology. They are interested in understanding the complexities, hurdles, and solutions encountered during the implementation of battery projects.
- **Raw material availability and cost of production:** This topic suggests that the audience is interested in the availability and cost aspects of raw materials used in battery production. They want to explore the supply chain, sourcing strategies, pricing factors, and potential challenges in acquiring the necessary raw materials for battery manufacturing.
- **Recycling Li-metal batteries:** This suggestion highlights the audience's interest in sustainable practices and the circular economy. They want to learn more about the recycling methods and processes specific to lithium-metal batteries. This topic reflects their concern for environmental impact and the desire to explore sustainable approaches to battery waste management.

Overall, the audience's suggestions indicate a strong interest in various aspects of battery technology, including economic analysis, technical advancements, optimisation strategies, sustainability, and challenges in practical implementation. These topics provide valuable guidance for curating relevant and engaging content that aligns with the audience's interests and expectations.

Figure 30: Percentage of new information delivered to the audience.

9.2. Questionnaire and scientific publication

A survey with a cross-sectional design was utilised to gather valuable insights from the partners of the **SOLID4B cluster** and structure the systematic questions for writing a scientific research manuscript. It's important to note that the questionnaire was developed after conducting a comprehensive analysis of audience feedback on participation in **SOLID4B cluster** activities and engaging in extensive dialogue with cluster partners. These interactions were crucial in creating a clear roadmap for the cluster, ensuring that the questionnaire effectively captured the varied motivations, approaches, and challenges encountered by project stakeholders. This iterative process of designing the questionnaire emphasised the significance of stakeholder engagement and participatory decision-making in shaping the research methodology, thereby enhancing the relevance and applicability of the study findings. Compared to interviews and observation, the questionnaire is a widely used data collection tool in empirical research. The questionnaire included multiple-choice (closed) and descriptive (open) questions. The most common data collection method is online questionnaires due to their efficiency and cost-effectiveness in gathering large amounts of information, streamlining the data collection and analysis process. As indicated in Table 1, the questionnaire comprised four main sections: motivation, approach, implementation, general open questions, and their corresponding question types.

Table 1. Structure and questions in the questionnaire.

No	Section	Questions	Type
1	Clustering motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What are the primary drivers for collaborating and clustering with other projects? ii. Do you collaborate because of inherent benefits or whether it is an obligation from the EU? iii. Throughout your project, what benefits does your organisation expect from collaborating with other projects? iv. Are there any specific challenges or barriers to effective collaboration and knowledge exchange with partners from other projects? v. Do you have any recommendations for the SOLID4B cluster to overcome the mentioned challenges? 	The i-iv are closed questions, and v is open.
2	Collaborating approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> vi. What is the optimum frequency, according to you, for a common cluster activity vii. If there is a confidentiality agreement between all the cluster projects, what are you willing to share with other projects? viii. Do you think a shared repository of related projects with the following 	Closed questions.

		information helps collaboration and increase synergies	
3	Networking implementation	<p>ix. Do you actively seek opportunities to engage with partners from different projects in external events, conferences, or research networks to expand the cluster's reach and influence?</p> <p>x. The cluster leader has strived to organise events at the cluster level every six months. Are you aware of these events? Have you received regular updates about the progress? Would you like to participate actively in such events?</p>	Closed questions.
4	Experience and expectation	<p>xi. From your experience, do you have any example of a successful collaboration/ clustering across different projects? According to you, what are the factors that contributed to its success?</p> <p>xii. When it comes to the SOLID4B cluster, are the expectations and opportunities arising from cross-project collaboration clear to you?</p>	Open questions.

The clustering activities have provided valuable insights for publishing scientific studies in administrative science. The research explores the factors and dynamics of clustering and interproject collaboration within the context of projects under Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020. Using a survey-based method, Takwa Benissa, from the SPINMATE project, and Anish Patil, from the ADVAGEN project, analyse the essential aspects related to the perception of clustering, the willingness to share information under legal confidentiality, and the motivations for engaging with partners from different projects. The survey was conducted using Microsoft Forms and was distributed to the consortia of eight EU projects participating in the **SOLID4B cluster**. Notably, the questionnaire was carefully designed after conducting a thorough analysis of the SOLID4B case and engaging in comprehensive discussions with the project officer, project coordinators, and communication & dissemination managers from all participating projects. These discussions aimed to establish a clear direction for the cluster, ensuring the questionnaire was relevant and valuable for all participants. Data analysis was conducted within the same platform, facilitating efficient data processing and visualisation. The results indicate that most respondents (48 out of 55) consider clustering a valuable asset, signalling a positive change in perspective. Concerns related to confidentiality were addressed through nuanced insights, with respondents demonstrating a readiness to share routine best practices, significant breakthroughs, and deliverables within a legally protected framework.

Additionally, a significant majority (40 out of 55) expressed strong interest in collaborative efforts, emphasising a collective commitment to expanding activities beyond individual project boundaries. The research underscores the significance of clustering with other projects to maximise the impact of the Horizon program, expand stakeholder networks, and share knowledge and achievements in research and innovation. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the motivations and challenges associated with clustering and collaboration

within Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects. Ultimately, the results pave the way for informed strategies to promote a dynamic and interconnected research community.

10. Summaries

10.1. Conclusions

The **SOLID4B cluster** has effectively fostered collaboration among European-level projects focused on solid-state batteries. These projects have been instrumental in translating research data into valuable knowledge for various stakeholders, including researchers, government/policymakers, and industries, to advance R&D in the field of electric vehicles. The exchange of knowledge and experience among different projects has significantly contributed to maximizing communication and dissemination of achievements and impacts within the cluster. Through dedicated events, the **SOLID4B cluster** has provided a platform to discuss, promote, and share ideas related to solid-state battery systems and e-mobility technologies, thereby translating research data into valuable knowledge for diverse stakeholders.

10.2. Recommendations

Based on the three events' results above, the online webinar, the 1st and 2nd hybrid workshops, and various themes covering the ASSB topic indicate that the spirit of clustering activities is unavoidable. All eight projects under the **SOLID4B cluster** should continue fruitful collaboration through different activities to strengthen the coherency and consistency of what we have achieved so far. **SPINMATE** has finished being the event's lead. Further, the other 7 cluster projects, ADVAGEN, AM4BAT, HIDDEN, PULSELION, SEATBELT, SOLID, and PSIONIC, should take over the lead for hosting events in the name of **SOLID4B cluster** to keep the existence of beneficial collaboration and keep the positive impact from knowledge dissemination.